

NOIRLab Launches *Cool Neighbors* Citizen Science Project

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A known brown dwarf seen moving in a *Cool Neighbors* “flipbook” movie of WISE data. The brown dwarf’s 2010 (2021) position is indicated by a red (blue) arrow in each panel, and its orange-ish hue signifies its cold temperature. *Cool Neighbors* volunteers scour for more subtle examples of motion relative to background stars/galaxies, indicative of a very nearby distance. Credit: NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/WISE/NEOWISE/coolneighbors.org/A. Meisner

Have we found all of the Sun’s closest neighbors? Our census of the solar neighborhood, especially its population of cold and faint brown dwarfs, is still growing at a brisk clip (Kirkpatrick et al. 2021). Brown dwarfs, intermediate in mass between the smallest red dwarf stars and the largest giant exoplanets, provide unique laboratories for revealing the low-mass terminus of star formation, and by proxy, the atmospheric properties of Jupiter-like giant exoplanets.

In today’s data-driven astronomy era, there exist vast archives of wide-area survey data, which have immense potential for unveiling new cold and nearby neighbors of the Sun, including surveys such as WISE, DECaLS, and DES (Wright et al. 2010; Dey et al. 2019; Abbott et al. 2018).

However, large datasets already in hand have yet to be fully searched for substellar objects. Completing the local Galactic census will require a combination of available techniques, including machine learning and citizen science. The citizen science approach for discovering brown dwarfs has proven particularly valuable in disentangling true — and extremely rare — substellar object discoveries from much more common artifacts, such as image noise and diffraction spikes.

Co-founded in 2017 by NSF’s NOIRLab astronomer Aaron Meisner, the *Backyard Worlds: Planet 9* citizen science project has pioneered the use of crowdsourcing for discovery of nearby brown dwarfs. *Backyard Worlds: Planet 9* has

discovered nearly 4,000 brown dwarf candidates to date (Meisner et al. 2020), which have been followed up with NOIRLab facilities including the SOAR Telescope, both telescopes of the International Gemini Observatory, and the Víctor M. Blanco 4-meter Telescope. Still, *Backyard Worlds: Planet 9* is not optimized for discovering brown dwarfs, but rather for finding hypothesized planets in the outer solar system.

In June 2023, the NOIRLab-led *Backyard Worlds: Cool Neighbors* spinoff project officially launched on Zooniverse. *Cool Neighbors* is the next generation of *Backyard Worlds*, catalyzing more rapid discovery of cold brown dwarfs by using machine learning to preselect the candidates shown to online volunteers. *Cool Neighbors* thus exemplifies the growing trend of synergistic cooperation between citizen science and machine learning, the latter sometimes referred to as “artificial intelligence.”

The *Cool Neighbors* launch was supported by an innovative type of NASA grant called the Citizen Science Seed Funding Program (CSSFP), meant to incubate exciting crowdsourcing projects in their early, pre-launch phases. Thanks to this NASA funding and additional support from NOIRLab, three summer undergraduate interns — Austin Humphreys (Maryland), Grady Robbins (Florida), and Eden Schapera

(Georgia) — were able to experience cutting-edge research at NOIRLab while building and launching *Cool Neighbors*.

Since launch, *Cool Neighbors* has been highly successful at both engaging the general public and discovering brown dwarfs. Within just its first few months, *Cool Neighbors* had already exceeded a million total “classifications” and blazed through its initial set of 30,000 brown dwarf candidates. Thanks in part to *Cool Neighbors*, the *Backyard Worlds* project as a whole has now surpassed 10 million total classifications since launch! *Cool Neighbors* has also reached a diverse group of participants drawn from all 50 US states plus Washington, DC, and at least 89 countries across the globe. In September 2023, *Cool Neighbors* founding co-investigator and amateur astronomer Dan Caselden was awarded the Astronomical Society of the Pacific’s [Gordon Myers Amateur Achievement Award](#).

As *Cool Neighbors* turns toward following up its initial crop of brown dwarf candidates, infrared-capable NOIRLab facilities such as Gemini, Blanco, and SOAR are likely to play key roles. Given that *Cool Neighbors* participants are sifting through tens of thousands of brown dwarf candidates faster than expected, *Cool Neighbors* also plans a pivot toward using the NOIRLab Source Catalog (Nidever et al. 2021), which covers 85% of the sky with excellent red-optical sensitivity, for future preselection of its substellar candidates. The combination of machine learning and citizen science demonstrated by *Cool Neighbors* will only grow in importance over the coming years, as the Vera C. Rubin Observatory’s Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST) creates its astronomical catalog an order of magnitude larger than any before.

References

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- [Wright, E. L., et al. 2010, AJ, 140, 1868](#)